

THE ROLE OF PRIVATE EMPLOYMENT AGENCIES IN PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT TO THE POPULATION DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract. *The purpose of this research paper is to determine the role of private employment agencies and their legal status in providing employment to the population. The further development of the activities of private employment agencies, problems related to legal regulation and employment issues are analyzed in different and similar aspects with government agencies.*

Keywords: *labor market, pandemic, private employment agency, recruitment agency, ILO, license.*

Introduction

It is also pertinent to acknowledge that in ensuring employment of the population, every person, regardless of experience, qualifications, region of residence, gender and social status, strives to get a decent job in the labor market. Considering that the natural population growth of the planet increases by 227,398 people per day and by 96,617,035 people per year, ensuring employment of the population is an urgent problem for the world community to solve. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated January 28, 2022 sets the tasks of "... effectively organizing the activities of assistants to district (city) khokims and youth leaders on issues of entrepreneurship development, ensuring employment of the population and reducing poverty, introduced as a new institution in mahallas." Today, countries realize the need to use all intermediaries in the labor market infrastructure to ensure employment. According to the International Labor Organization, the role of recruitment agencies in the growth of the global labor market, its transformation into a flexible and mobile form over the past two decades is incomparable.

Materials and methods

The concept of recruiting is interpreted differently in a number of foreign sources. In particular, the word "recruitment" comes from the French word "recruiter", which literally means to hire a person, to recruit for paid military service. In German, the equivalent of this term is "recruiting" - to recruit, to recruit. This word has the same meaning in English [1].

In particular, academician K. Abdurakhmanov defines "recruiting activities as entrepreneurial activities consisting of service processes related to the search for suitable employees (jobs) for employers (job seekers) in order to make a profit" [2]. In addition to searching, hiring, selecting and evaluating jobs for the unemployed, recruiting agencies also help candidates adapt to the requirements of the rapidly changing labor market in the era of globalization. Indeed, the importance of this task was noted by academician K.Kh. Abdurakhmanov, Doctor of Economics, Professor N.K. Zakirov expresses as "... identifying fundamental problems in these areas based on the analysis of patterns and trends in the

development of the labor and employment market and preparing scientifically based recommendations on ways and methods of solving them, developing models that help improve the efficiency of the labor market, preparing conclusions to clarify long-term plans for economic and social development of the country and the region based on labor force forecasts" [3]. As a private form of employment, recruitment agencies legally entered the labor market of Uzbekistan in 2018. Naturally, the novelty of the activity and the lack of complete information about employment agencies among our citizens led to a number of problems. Accordingly, the activities of recruitment agencies require improving legal, organizational and economic mechanisms. For this purpose, a systematic approach, methods of analysis and synthesis, and forecasting were used in the research process. The above points also indicate the need for a separate study of the activities of non-governmental employment agencies, along with state employment services, in solving the problems of improving the quality of life of the population and ensuring employment in our country.

Results

Additionally, it should be noted that due to the coronavirus pandemic, the global labor market is experiencing the most serious crisis since World War II. According to the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the unemployment rate in Uzbekistan during the pandemic reached almost 2 million people. As a result of the quarantine restrictions, about 500 thousand of our compatriots were unable to travel to work in foreign countries [4].

Moreover, it is important to highlight that external and internal migration in the countries of the world has practically come to naught. The volume of cross-border remittances received by the country in 2020 amounted to \$2.4 billion, which is \$156 million or 6 percent less than in the same period last year [5]. In such conditions, it is natural that the importance of private employment agencies, that is, recruiting agencies, in the employment of the unemployed and the restoration of external labor migration to its previous level will increase significantly. In the global labor market, such organizations as TEK systems US, Hays plc, Cegos France, Modis, Harvey Nash, Michael Page International UK, Heidrick&Struggles, Futurestep, Antal International, Michael Page International US are considered the strongest and leading agencies in the field of personnel selection services [6].

Abroad, private employment agencies are called personnel agencies and, as an independent entity, provide services to enterprises (employers) and job seekers. Recruitment agencies and their activities are considered so effective that they are even regulated by law on an international scale. Initially, the International Labor Organization adopted Convention No. 181 "On Private Employment Agencies" in 1949, "On Employment Promotion and Protection against Unemployment" in 1988 and "On Private Employment Agencies" in 1997. Recruitment companies contribute to the employment of 8-10 million people worldwide annually. However, the practice of private organizations in our country to employ citizens in our republic and abroad has not yet been fully formed. The legal basis for this activity was created in the Republic of Uzbekistan with the adoption of the Law "On Private Employment Agencies" in 2018. As of July 15, 2020, 103 organizations are registered in the register of private employment agencies in our republic, and the number of organizations that have received a license is 36.

According to the Law "On Private Employment Agencies", private employment agencies can provide the following types of services: job selection for job seekers in the Republic of Uzbekistan; recruitment of personnel for employers; employment of persons seeking employment outside the Republic of Uzbekistan; information and consulting services in the field of

employment. Now private employment agencies are prohibited from charging a fee for the services provided to employ citizens abroad. Private employment agencies licensed to employ citizens abroad cannot charge a fee exceeding a one-time amount of the basic calculation amount, i.e. 223 thousand soums, for information and consulting services. It is prohibited to provide services to citizens without concluding contracts with a foreign employer and partner, and these contracts must be posted on the official website of private employment agencies.

Over the past period, 104 legal entities were registered in the register of private employment agencies, and currently 18 of them are licensed to employ citizens abroad [7]. The activity of employing persons seeking employment outside the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out on the basis of a license. That is, without a license, an agency cannot carry out activities to employ persons seeking employment outside the Republic of Uzbekistan. The illegal actions of some private employment agency managers have also cast a shadow on the activities of legally operating employment agencies and have caused citizens to feel distrust in the activities of private employment agencies. Therefore, further reform of the activities of private employment agencies and restoration of citizens' trust are urgent issues.

The draft Presidential Decree "On measures to fundamentally improve licensing and permitting procedures", developed by the Ministry of Justice jointly with relevant organizations, also covers some issues related to the activities of private employment agencies. According to the current Regulation "On the procedure for licensing activities on the employment of persons seeking work outside the Republic of Uzbekistan", to obtain a license, it is necessary to submit an extract from the order on appointment to a managerial position and documents confirming the manager's higher education. Appendix 5 to the draft Decree sets out measures aimed at further reducing and simplifying the procedures for obtaining licensing and permitting documents.

According to it, it is envisaged to abolish the submission of an extract from the order on appointment to a managerial position and documents confirming the manager's higher education by integrating into a single national labor system. It is also envisaged to include in the licensing requirements and conditions the requirement to enter each agreement concluded between private employment agencies and citizens into a specially created electronic information system and its constant updating. I would also like to make the following proposals for the further development of the activities of private employment agencies. According to current legislation, agencies are issued licenses for an unlimited period.

Discussion

According to foreign experience, the activities of private banking agencies are not limited to the presence of a database containing information about clients, employees and company employees in the agency. [8]. The level of professionalism of the agency's employees is determined by the level of its authority, and the professional level of the employees is determined by the quality of the agency's work [9]. This may be due to the fact that there are many private travel agencies in Uzbekistan specializing in travel services. In our opinion, licensing should be carried out to minimize risks. Licensing of private banking agencies can be extended indefinitely in order to improve the efficiency of their activities, as well as to ensure their reliability, trustworthiness and reliability. In this case, the license is issued for a certain period and can be extended. This procedure is valid in South Korea and the Czech Republic for 3 years, in the Philippines for 4 years, in Japan for 3 years and then can be extended for 5 years.

The purpose of this measure is to increase the responsibility of private banking agencies. Amalietta had a license to work in some agencies, but she was not allowed to work. The Mazursky

District Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan granted the investigation's petition to extend the Agency's license for activities not related to its activities abroad. In turn, the officer said that he did not intend to leave his job abroad. At the same time, according to him, robbers are people who do not want to become victims of hatred or hate crimes. He is currently under house arrest. But "rice cooking" was not in the shameful context of "fid" [10]. This system, created for the purpose of its further development, is not universal.

There are several mosques and private baths in Khorasan. Unfortunately, their accelerator has become a brand. In 2019-2020, control over private banking will lead to the destruction of about 3,300 hectares of forest in Russia, Turkey, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Bulgaria, Bangladesh, Saudi Arabia, Belarus, Croatia, Japan, Estonia, Uzbekistan, Ukraine, Israel, Germany, Greece, Poland. However, they do not violate license requirements and conditions. According to the data, 11 branches of private banks suffered losses in the amount of 71.8 billion rubles [11]. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "This is a great honor for us. According to one of the group members, "we wanted to express our gratitude to two people for helping to fight banditry, as well as for helping to fight banditry."

According to the Agency for Migration and Migration Affairs under the Government of Tajikistan, migrants from Tajikistan do not use the services of state unitary enterprises. According to the Jogorku Kenesh, about 8,000 people are served in this area, and about 3 million people in Uzbekistan. The Huawei agency published a study according to which migrants from Uzbekistan come to European countries, Japan and Japan to find high-quality, high-quality and safe work. The activities of private gang agencies should be aimed at ensuring that all the conditions necessary for their activities are met, as well as that their activities are aimed at expanding the rights and freedoms of gang members. Since the messenger's activity is prohibited for distribution throughout the country, it can be blocked for several days. This approach does not require much time and money and is suitable for optimizing public procurement costs.

In addition, according to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an applicant for a license to provide employment services to persons seeking work outside the republic is required to reserve funds in the amount of fifty thousand US dollars in the Fund for the Support of Citizens Working Abroad and the Protection of Their Rights and Interests under the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, this amount may not be enough to compensate for the losses of all migrants who have entered into contractual relations with a private employment agency. Therefore, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations has put forward a proposal to set this amount at 8,500 times the basic calculation value (approximately 200 thousand US dollars).

Critical opinions are expressed regarding the amendment to the amount of "8,500 times the minimum wage" in Part Four of Article 13 and Paragraph Seven of Part One of Article 23 of the Law [12]. In our opinion, this also does not solve the problem. In this case, contributing this amount of money to the fund may worsen the financial situation of private employment agencies, which will negatively affect their activities, in particular the effective organization of their activities, competitiveness and attraction of qualified personnel. If we turn to foreign experience on this issue, then in many countries a differentiated form of security deposit is used. The main criterion here is that the amount of payment is determined by the number of migrants sent by private employment agencies to work abroad [13].

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it can be asserted that we can say that if the circumstances that hinder the development of private employment agencies are not eliminated, this industry will lose its position. The goal of any private agency is to independently solve three problems: 1) understand the customer's needs for personnel; 2) find among the offers the most appropriate to these needs; 3) check previous candidates to guarantee the customer maximum efficiency and organization of future employees. In Uzbekistan, over the past 4 years, the licenses of 71 private employment agencies have been revoked (mostly voluntarily). Currently, only 6 operating agencies remain. The Ministry of Labor has warned about fraudsters who take money from citizens, promising to send them to work abroad. According to the law, an employment agency does not have the right to take money from a citizen for employment abroad.

Since 2018, when private employment agencies were allowed to operate in Uzbekistan, 71 employment agency licenses have been revoked. In 59 cases, the application was submitted by the enterprises themselves, and criminal cases were initiated against 12 agencies. According to him, there are 6 private employment agencies operating today. In fact, there are 9 private employment agencies that have licenses and are authorized to provide employment abroad, but 2 of them had their licenses temporarily suspended for 6 months due to failure to comply with the reserve of funds in the amount of 800 times the minimum wage, and another was subject to additional inspection due to complaints and appeals, and its license was suspended for 10 days. Therefore, legal regulation of the activities of private employment agencies created in recent years and the development of this emerging industry are among the pressing issues of today. It is necessary to further improve the activities of private employment agencies, develop organized recruitment of citizens as a priority form of labor migration, and control their activities.

First of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following areas: analysis of the scientific basis of private employment agencies; their specialization based on foreign experience in order to be competitive in the global labor market; organization of private employment agencies in rural areas; specialization of private employment agencies in a certain segment of the rural labor market; establishment of cooperation with district BKM; stimulation of labor export abroad; creation of private agencies to work with categories of the population that are less competitive in the rural labor market; training of qualified recruiters, consultants and managers working in private employment agencies, and improving their qualifications abroad; use of various personnel selection technologies in their work; use of unique methods, techniques and approaches in searching for and selecting applicants. Therefore, in modern conditions, the development of private employment agencies and providing them with comprehensive assistance is of great importance. At the same time, it is advisable to launch a unified national program for informing about labor, protect the rights and interests of migrant workers, employ migrant workers who have returned from abroad, and implement such measures as free vocational training.

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